

FUNCTIONALLY GRADIENT SYNTACTIC FOAMS

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SUMMARY

The present study explores the procedure to fabricate functionally gradient syntactic foams (FGSFs) and further analyze their quasi-static mechanical properties. Several FGSF specimens having similar density with different layer sequencing are fabricated. Compressive properties for each arrangement are compared and crack propagation is analyzed.

Keywords: Functionally Gradient, Syntactic Foam, Microballoons, Mechanical Properties, Energy Absorption.

ABSTRACT

The present study explores the procedure to fabricate functionally gradient syntactic foam (FGSF) with a gradient in the microballoon radius ratio and further analyzes quasi-static mechanical properties. The volume fraction of microballoons in each layer is kept constant at 60% to maintain uniformity in the structure. Several FGSF specimens having similar density are fabricated with different layer sequencing. The different layers are integrated before major solidification takes place. Quasi-static compression testing is then performed on the cured FGSF samples using MTS-810 servo hydraulic machine. Compressive strength and energy absorption values for each arrangement are compared. It is found that the stress plateau in integrated FGSF composites extends to 60% strain compared to 20% strain for plain syntactic foams. The integrated FGSF shows dramatic increment in yield strength and energy absorption compared to adhesively bonded FGSF. It is also found that the compressive strength and energy absorption of integrated FGSF composites can be varied based on arrangement of the layers. Crack propagation of the FGSFs shown unique characterization based on layer sequencing.

1. INTRODUCTION

Syntactic foams have attracted significant importance as a weight sensitive material for aerospace, space and naval structures core material [1]. Syntactic foams are three-phase, microballoons, matrix, and voids, particulate composite core material. These foams also gained significant importance as core materials in sandwich composites due to their excellent properties such as high energy absorption, compressive strength, damage tolerance [2,3] and low moisture absorption [4]. Sandwich composites are

special type of composites having significant advantages such as high specific strength and bending stiffness [5]. Sandwich composites comprise of two thin but stiff face sheets attached on either side of a lightweight, thick slab known as core. These exceptional properties made them attractive for aerospace [6,7], naval [8] and deep sea applications [9] where huge hydrostatic pressures are involved.

The compressive properties of syntactic foams can be altered by varying the matrix material, type of microballoon, volume fraction and radius ratio (η) [10]. The radius ratio (η) is defined as the ratio of inner radius (r_i) to outer radius (r_o) of microballoons. Higher radius ratio (η) leads to thinner wall thickness with lower density, and lower strength [11,12]. Several studies are also available on the effect of microballoon volume fraction and radius ratio on the quasi-static compressive and high strain rate properties of syntactic foams [11-13]. Even though the strength of low density microballoons is low, they exhibit a larger stress-plateau compared to higher density microballoons in syntactic foams, a typical characterization of high energy absorbing materials [3,13,14]. Several researchers have also studied the usage of syntactic foams in gradient structures [15-18]. Gradient structures can be created by two methods, either by varying the volume fraction of microballoons or the radius ratio (η) of microballoons. The schematic representation of FGSF with the radius ratio (η) variation in microballoon is shown in Fig. 1. It is important to note that the outer diameters of the microballoons are the same.

It is found that the compressive properties of gradient syntactic foams are not significantly improved by varying the volume fraction of microballoons (V_{mb}) [10]. Additionally, the V_{mb} variation in gradient structure subjects the material to non-uniform stress concentrations and varying coefficient of thermal expansion. The non-uniform stresses leads to catastrophic failure originating in the matrix rich side of the specimen, especially when the matrix is a brittle polymer such as epoxy resin. Furthermore, the difference in thermal expansion coefficient leads to warping of the material after being exposed to different environmental conditions [17,18]. Gupta [10,19] has managed to overcome the above shortcomings of volume fraction variant FGSF structure by creating the FGSF with variation of radius ratio (η). However, the FGSF is fabricated by joining the individual syntactic foam layers using an adhesive material. The properties of adhesively bonded structures are known to depend on the type of adhesive material used for bonding the layers. It is found that peeling stresses are detrimental to the structure because of high transverse shear stresses [20].

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of FGSF with density variation and microballoon

Fig. 2. Pictorial representation of different FGFSF configurations used in this study

In the present study, five different layer sequence FGFSF specimens as shown in Fig. 2, are fabricated with layer over layer integrated technique, Fig. 2. These FGFSF specimens are tested for quasi-static flat-wise compressive properties on MTS-810 servo hydraulic machine. Four of the five configurations are kept symmetric in order to keep the composites coupling effects minimal. In order to compare the present fabrication technique with the adhesively bonded fabrication technique, a fifth configuration is fabricated with the same layer sequence as that of adhesively bonded FGFSF. The volume fraction is maintained constant at 60% in all the syntactic foam layers of FGFSF specimens. The void content in the specimens is calculated by means of density measurements. The crack propagation behavior is monitored and analyzed on the fractured sample to show the crack propagation and crushing of microballoons.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SET UP

2.1 Raw Materials

2.1.1 Glass microballoons

The glass microballoons used in this study are manufactured and supplied by 3M Company under the trade name of 'Scotchlite'. Physical properties of selected microballoons, supplied by the manufacturer, are presented in Table 1. The difference in wall thickness of different types of microballoons causes the difference in their density. The calculated radius ratio (η) for all types of microballoons is also given in Table 1.

2.1.2 Matrix system

Epoxy resin D.E.R. 332, manufactured by DOW Chemical Company along with an amine based hardener D.E.H. 24 and a C₁₂-C₁₄ aliphatic glycidylether diluent is used as the matrix system. The diluent is mixed with the epoxy resin in 5% by volume to reduce its viscosity. Reduction in viscosity makes it easier to mix higher volume fraction of particles in the matrix resin.

Table 1 Microballoons size distribution and radius ratio

Micro Balloon Type	Microballoon Size Distribution (μm)			Average True particle Density (kg/m^3)	Average Wall Thickness (μm)	Radius Ratio (η) 10 th percentile
	10 th percentile	50 th percentile	90 th percentile			
S22	20	35	60	220	S22	20
S32	20	40	75	320	S32	20
S38	15	40	75	380	S38	15
K46	15	40	70	460	K46	15

2.2 Fabrication of FGSF structure

The volume fraction of microballoons is maintained constant at 60% in each of the syntactic foam layer. First, the microballoons are mechanically mixed with the matrix system, and then poured in square aluminum mold. Thickness of each foam layer is maintained using aluminum strips on each side of the mold. The inner volume of the mold cavity is $305 \times 305 \times 20 \text{ mm}^3$. Flatness of the layer is maintained using a level indicator. Before the second layer is aligned to the base layer, the base layer is allowed to slightly solidify. Additional layers are prepared in a second mold and laid over the base layers to prepare a FGSF structure. The process continues until the last layer is set. The FGSF structure is kept under vacuum for 30 to 45 min to reduce the void content. Casted FGSF slabs are cured at room temperature for 24 hours and post cured at $100 \pm 3^\circ\text{C}$ for 3 hours. The cured samples are cut to produce test specimens as per ASTM standard.

2.3 Density measurement

The density of the fabricated syntactic foam composites is measured using ASTM C 271-94 standard. The density measurements produce porosity information. Porosity is a factor that affects the properties of syntactic foams. The fabricated samples have porosity within the micro balloons, known as closed cell porosity and also in the matrix material due to mechanical mixing process, known as open cell porosity. Calculated values of density and open cell porosity of fabricated syntactic foams are shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Measured densities and open cell porosity in flat-wise FGSF configurations

FGSF Configuration	Theoretical Density (kg/m^3)	Density (kg/m^3)	Open Cell porosity
K46-S38-S32-S22	655	629 ± 4.8	3.96 ± 0.7
K46-S22-S22-K46	652	623 ± 4.6	4.50 ± 0.7
S22-K46-K46-S22	652	627 ± 4.2	3.83 ± 0.6
S32-S38-S38-S32	658	622 ± 2.4	5.45 ± 0.4
S38-S32-S32-S38	658	628 ± 4.9	4.55 ± 0.7

2.4 Quasi- static flat-wise compression

Five samples of each of the five integrated FGSF configurations are tested for flat-wise compression properties on servo-hydraulic MTS machine according to ASTM C 365/C 365 M-05 standards. The specimens dimensions in quasi-static compression tests are maintained at approximately $32 \times 32 \times 16 \text{ mm}^3$. Samples are compressed at a loading rate of 1.3 mm/min. Load, displacement and compressive yield strength values are recorded.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The FGSF composites in this research have similar density, even though they are fabricated with different layer sequencing. The specimens S22-K46-K46-S22, K46-S22-S22-K46, S32-S38-S38-S32, and S38-S32-S32-S38 and K46-S38-S32-S22 have symmetric and asymmetric configurations of FGSF, respectively. The asymmetrical structure results are also compared with that of adhesively bonded FGSF fabricated with the same layer sequencing. The five FGSF configurations are tested and analyzed for flat-wise compression properties. The FGSF compression results are compared with plain syntactic foams and adhesively bonded FGSFs.

From Fig. 4(a), it is observed that the stress plateau of the FGSF extends from 8 to 60% of strain in contrast to an extension from 10 to 20% for plain syntactic foams with similar density. The energy absorption of FGSF is found to increase by 200% compared to plain foams. This improvement in energy absorption is due to the high energy absorption of the low density layers while the high density layers contribute more to the strength of the whole FGSF. Furthermore, the FGSF show an improvement in compressive yield strength and energy absorption over adhesively bonded FGSF. From Fig. 4(a), it is evident that the compressive yield strength values increased from around 32.7 MPa for adhesively bonded material to 49 MPa for FGSF, an increase of 50%. It is also found that the overall energy absorption of FGSF increased by 75%, from around 16.5 MPa to 28.9 MPa, compared to that of adhesively bonded FGSF. This improvement in compressive properties can be attributed to the difference in interfacial bonding between the two fabrication methods. In this study, FGSFs are fabricated using the chemical interaction between layers rather than an adhesive material. The properties of the adhesive FGSF specimen also depends on adhesive material in addition to matrix material, type of microballoon, volume fraction of microballoons, and radius ratio (η). Therefore, it can be concluded that the fabrication method used in this study enhances the compressive properties as compared to adhesively bonded FGSF technique.

The flat-wise compressive properties are obtained from graphs (Fig. 4(b)), and are shown in Table 3. From Fig. 4(b) and Table 3, the compressive yield strength, modulus and energy absorption of FGSF with S32 and S38 microballoons configurations are higher compared to other FGSF configurations used in this study. This is due to the fact that the flat-wise compression properties of FGSF structures always depend on the weakest layer in the configuration. The weakest layer in S32 and S38 microballoons configurations is S32, whereas the weakest layer in S22 and K46 microballoons configurations is S22. Also, as the S22 microballoon has higher radius ratio, lower density and lower strength compared to S32 microballoon, the configuration of S32 and S38 microballoons show higher properties.

Fig. 4(a). Stress plateau comparison of FGSF, adhesively bonded FGSF and plain foam.

Fig. 4(b). Stress vs. strain plots for various FGSF configurations tested in this study.

Table 3 Flat-wise compressive properties of FGSF configurations

Type of FGSF Specimen	Average Compressive Modulus (MPa)	Average Compressive Yield Strength, (MPa)	Energy Absorption
S22-K46-K46-S22	703.3±10	42.54±0.9	31.0±1.2
K46-S22-S22-K46	722.7±20	42.72±1.6	26.42±0.5
S32-S38-S38-S32	795.0±15	60.34±0.3	32.50±0.2
S38-S32-S32-S38	783.9±13	60.89±0.8	28.22±0.6
K46-S38-S32-S22	722.4±17	49.38±1.4	28.98±0.5
Plain Foam	585.7±6	47.90±1.7	8.54±0.4

Moreover, from Fig. 4(b), it is also found that all stress-strain plots observed in symmetric FGSF configurations do not follow the same trend. It is observed that the stress-strain curve obtained from FGSF with S32 and S38 microballoons increased until yield point and continued a flat trend with fewer slopes until 50% of strain. Then curves slope increased dramatically until 60% of strain that can be considered as consolidation point. However, the stress-strain curves of FGSF with S22 and K46 configurations did not follow the smooth stress-strain curve. The curves tend to peak at 25-30% of strain corresponding to the stress level where the crack propagate into the K49 layer. The curves followed the smooth increasing until 60% of strain, ultimately reaching to its maximum consolidation point. The difference in stress-strain plots is due to the differences in radius ratio (η) of the microballoons in those configurations. The radius ratio (η) difference of S32 and S38 microballoons is small compared to the radius ratio difference in K46 and S22 microballoons. Due to this reason, in FGSF configuration with S22 and K46 microballoons, the densification of S22 completes at 25 to 30% of the strain. Thereafter the K46 microballoons resist deformation until the higher stress limit. On contrary, in S32 and S38 configuration, as the difference in radius ratio is small, the densification and crack propagation of S32 and S38 layers happens simultaneously.

From Fig. 4(b) and Table 3, it is also observed that the FGSF configurations with central denser layers, such as S22-K46-K46-S22, and S32-S38-S38-S32 have higher energy absorption when compared to their counter configurations. Additionally, the FGSF's with central denser layer configuration are structurally more stable. It is evident that the failure of structures always initiates at the weakest point. Therefore, the FGSF structures with two weakest layers (low density layers) at the center have more localized failures thereby causing over all structural instability. Alternatively, the structure with weakest layers as outer layers have less number of localized failures in addition to the two central stiffer layers giving stability to the structure. Hence, it can be inferred that the compressive properties of FGSF structures are dependent on the layer sequence.

Fig. 5 shows the crack propagation behavior of FGSF configurations with different layer sequencing. From Fig. 5, it is observed that the crack initiation always takes place in the weakest layer (low density layer) and then propagates towards the highest density layers upon further loading. In flat-wise compression, even though equal compressive stress is applied on all layers, crack initiates in the low density layer as the low density layers have low strength compared to other layers,. This crack propagation phenomena is evident in K46-S38-S32-S22 configuration, i.e., it shows that the crack initiate is reported in the weakest layer S22 and it propagated through S32, S38, and K46 layers upon further loading (Fig. 5(a)). Similar crack propagation behavior is also observed from Fig. 5(b) and Fig. 5(c), S32 and S38 microballoons FGSF configurations. In these configurations, the crack initiated in the weakest layer S32, and then propagated to S38 layer when further loading. Even in S22 and K46 microballoons FGSFs, the crack initiates in the weakest layer S22 and propagates towards higher density layer K46 as the load is increased.

From Fig. 5(b) and Fig. 5(c), it can be observed that even though the S32-S38-S38-S32 and S38-S32-S32-S38 FGSFs are fabricated with S32 and S38 microballoons, the crack propagation behavior is different. In Fig. 5(b), the crack propagated through S38 layers from S32 layers with partial densification of the S32 layers. From Fig. 5(c), it can be

Fig. 5(a). Crack initiation and densification of S22 layer (b). Crack initiation and densification of S32 layer (c). Crack propagation from S32 to S38 layer (d). Crack initiation and densification of S22. (e) Crack propagation from S22 to K46 layer observed that the complete densification and crushing of S32 layers is preceded by the crack propagation into the S38 layers.

This difference in crack propagation is due to the reason that the denser layers at the center resist load damage and deformation more compared to the less dense layers in the center. Moreover, the S32 layers in the central plane (S38-S32-S32-S38) have partial structural instability caused by the more localized failures of microballoons in the central layers. This structural instability is characterized by sliding and shear of S32 layer as well as peel out of part of S32 layer edges caused by secondary tensile stresses. The energy absorption in S32-S38-S38-S32 configuration is also found to be more than

that of S38-S32-S32-S38. Fig. 5(d) and Fig. 5(e) show the crack propagation behavior of K46 and S22 microballoons FGSF configurations. K46 and S22 microballoons FGSFs energy absorption also followed similar trend as that of S32 and S38 FGSF configurations. The energy absorption of S22-K46-K46-S22 FGSF is more compared to its counter part due to higher structural stability. Hence, it is evident that the crack propagation behavior also depends on the layer sequence of the FGSF in addition to volume fraction of microballoons, matrix material, and radius ratio (η).

4. CONCLUSIONS

Five different FGSF configurations with different layer sequencing are fabricated using layer over layer integrated technique. The FGSF specimens are tested under flat-wise compression. The results are compared with plain syntactic foams and as well adhesively bonded FGSF having similar density. Compared to plain syntactic foams, the FGSF's energy absorption has increased by 200% due to the extension of stress plateau from 20% to 60% strain. Furthermore, the FGSF showed an improvement of 50% and 75% in compressive yield strength and energy absorption respectively, compared to the adhesively bonded FGSF sample having similar layer sequence. The FGSF configurations with S32 and S38 microballoons have exhibited superior compressive properties compared to other FGSF configurations used in this study. Although the compressive yield strength values are found to be similar, the symmetric FGSF configurations with denser microballoons (S38 or K46) layers at the center showed an enhancement in energy absorption compared to their counterparts. The crack is always initiated in the weakest layer and propagated to higher density layers upon further loading. Therefore, it is evident that the energy absorption and crack propagation also depends on layer sequencing of the FGSF configuration.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank 3M Corporation, DOW Chemical Company for providing the raw materials used in this research. Also, constructive help of Dr. Phani Mylavarapu during this study is appreciated.

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